

Geospatial analysis of electrification to identify least cost technologies in order to accelerate universal access by 2030 in Mozambique

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Executive Summary

In order to achieve universal access, it is crucial that electrification plans are structured. There are numerous modeling tools that can be applied. In this work, OnSSET was used with the aim of determining the technologies that provide the most favorable cost for achieving access in the country.

The modeling results indicate that in order to achieve universal access by 2030, Mozambique must combine on-grid and off-grid solutions (SA and MG). On-grid solutions consist of (1) densification and (2) extension of the grid at an estimated cost of 1.73 billion and 2.96B respectively with a total share of 55%. The off-grid solutions consist of (3) Mini-Grids and (4) SA with an estimated cost of 0.44B and 2.98B respectively. The total investment cost is 8 billion dollars. A combined additional capacity will be 1798 MW where 731 MW are Off-grid and 1062 MW are grid. Considering that 52% of the digitalization of the distribution network was used for modelling purposes, it is necessary to improve the calibration of the model, so we recommend investing in data collection.

1. Introduction

Mozambique is committed to achieving universal access by 2030, and in order for Sustainable Development Goal 7 to be realised, implementation policies have been designed that focus on clean energy technologies. Currently, the electrification rate in the country is 53.4%, of which 46.3% concerns the urban population through the On-Grid and 7.1% concerns the rural population through pv mini-grids and isolated systems. However, the challenge of electrification still remains, as more than 40 per cent of the population still does not have access to it due to several factors such as the dispersion of the population, which is why it is crucial mapping these areas in order to identify accessible technologies in the respective locations.

2. Objective and aims

This work aims to evaluate areas of influence to identify locations to be electrified in Mozambique through technologies that present the lowest investment cost (LCOE) in order to achieve universal access in 2030 in the country.

Some questions can be raised:

- Where are the places that need to be electrified?
- Lower-cost technologies can be used to achieve universal access by 2030
- How much investment might be needed?
- Split between grid vs off-grid

2. Methodology

The modelling was done using OnSSET, a spatial electrification tool to estimate, analyse the scenarios for cost effective electrification options. The key following assumption was considered (1) start year 2023, (2) 30km buffer of the national electricity grid and cost per connection not exceeding 3000 Usd (4) the lowest demand level is 3 with 803 kWh/HH/year for rural areas and 3000 kWh/HH/year for urban areas and reference prices for infrastructure development according to the 2018-2027 Electricity Master Plan. The results generated in the OnSSET were visualized through the QGIS and the Ms Excel.

Detailed Assumptions

To run the scenarios, the following parameters were considered:

Population Data:

- Population in 2023: 32,419,747
- Projected Population in 2030: 38,689,102
- Urban Ratio: 34% in 2023
- Projected to increase to 36% by 2030

Residential Demand Targets:

Urban Settlements:

- Tier 5: Approximately 3000 kWh per household per year

Rural Settlements:

- Tier 3: Approximately 803 kWh per household per year

Grid Buffer:

Households within 30 km of the National Grid are considered to have potential for grid connection.

Technology Costs:

- Solar Home Systems (SHS): \$9620 per kW

Diesel Systems:

- Stand-alone Diesel: \$938 per kW
- Diesel for Mini-Grids: \$721 per kW

Mini-Grid Technologies:

- Photovoltaic (MG PV): \$1540 per kW
- Hydro (MG Hydro): \$3000 per kW
- Wind (MG Wind): \$2800 per kW

Operational Costs:

- Grid Generation Cost: \$0.10 per kWh (based on estimates)
- Diesel Fuel Price: \$1.30 per liter (based on expected market value)

These parameters provide a comprehensive basis for running various electrification scenarios, enabling an evaluation of both on-grid and off-grid solutions to achieve universal access to electricity in Mozambique by 2030. The population data is the basis to estimate future demand, while the urban ratio for distinguishing between urban and rural electrification needs. Residential demand targets are set to different tiers based on settlement types to reflect realistic consumption levels.

The detailed technology costs for various power generation methods, including solar home systems, diesel, and different mini-grid technologies, are crucial for cost-benefit analyses. Grid generation and diesel fuel prices are essential for calculating operational expenses and ensuring the economic feasibility of the proposed solutions.

Additional Considerations

Grid Expansion and Densification:

Grid Expansion: Involves extending the existing grid infrastructure to new areas. This is estimated to cost approximately \$2.96 billion.

Grid Densification: Focuses on increasing the connectivity within areas already served by the grid, with an estimated cost of \$1.73 billion.

Off-Grid Solutions:

Mini-Grids: Small-scale, localized grids that can operate independently or be connected to the larger grid. The total estimated cost for mini-grids is \$0.44 billion. Mini-grids can use various technologies including PV, hydro, and wind.

Stand-Alone Systems (SA): Individual power systems for households or small communities, with an estimated cost of \$2.98 billion. These systems are crucial for remote and sparsely populated areas where extending the grid is not cost-effective.

Investment and Capacity Requirements

To achieve universal access, the total investment required is estimated at \$8 billion. This includes the costs for both on-grid and off-grid solutions. The combined additional capacity needed is 1798 MW. The breakdown of this capacity between mini-grids and stand-alone systems (85 MW for mini-grids and 646 MW for stand-alone systems) will depend on further detailed planning and resource availability.

Model Calibration and Data Collection

Given that 52% of the distribution network digitization was used for modeling purposes, it is vital to enhance the accuracy of the model by improving data collection and calibration. Better data will enable more precise planning and implementation of electrification strategies. Therefore, we recommend investing in comprehensive data collection efforts to refine the model and ensure it reflects real-world conditions as closely as possible.

3. Results

Analysis of the Baseline Scenario

Analyzing the baseline scenario, it is observed that in 2024, electrification in Mozambique is predominantly achieved through the expansion and densification of the national electrical grid. This approach has been effective in covering a larger area, especially in provincial capitals, with the southern region of the country having the highest coverage.

In the central and northern regions, there is greater population dispersion, which makes the penetration of mini-grids more significant. Comparing the map of the baseline scenario with the map of the OnSSET modeling results for 2030, it is concluded that more stand-alone systems need to be introduced and the expansion and densification of the grid need to continue.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the total investment required to achieve universal access to electricity by 2030 is estimated at 8.03 billion USD. Of this total, 94.5% (7.59 billion USD) is allocated to investments in grid expansion and densification as well as stand-alone systems. The remaining 5.5% is allocated to investments in mini-grids, predominantly in the central and northern regions of the country.

To achieve the goal of universal access to electricity by 2030, Mozambique will need a multifaceted approach that combines grid expansion with the implementation of off-grid solutions such as mini-grids and stand-alone systems. The majority of the investment will be concentrated on grid expansion and densification, reflecting the need for robust infrastructure to support the growing demand for electricity. However, mini-grids will continue to play a crucial role, especially in areas with dispersed populations, ensuring that all regions of the country have reliable access to electricity.

Result 1: Current situation 2024

Figure1: Baseline Scenario, 2024

Result 2: The situation in 2030

Mozambique

- Grid
- Mini Grid Hydro
- Mini Grid Photovoltaic Hybrid
- Stand Alone Photovoltaic

0 250 500 km

Figure 2. Modelled Scenario, 2030

Total Capacity (MW) 2024 – 2030: 1 798

Figure 3: Estimated additional capacity to achieve universal access in 2030

Total Investment 2024 – 2030: 8 036 (Million USD)

Figure 4: Estimated investments to achieve universal access in 2030 for Mozambique.

5. Discussion

The current (2024) ratio to the electrification gap in Mozambique, is 47% for universal access.

In rural areas, the challenge is even greater due to the dispersed population. Related to this factor is the ability of rural communities to pay for energy services.

One of the main challenges for the improvement of the calibration of the model and consequently of the results is the lack of data on the distribution lines.

The results show that the technologies to be adopted to achieve universal access are SA and PV mini-grid in rural areas and grid extension in urban areas.

As SA is implemented by the private sector in the country, it is important to align government plans in terms of regions/locations for the implementation of these technologies.

7. Conclusion

In order to achieve 100% electrification rate for Mozambique until 2030, there are options as the least cost electrification for different settlements in Mozambique which we have to consider such as extend and densification of existing grid, stand-alone PV systems, hydro and PV mini grids systems. The people in the urban areas can be connected to the existing grid or the grid can be extended while the people in the rural areas can be electrified with stand-alone PV systems and mini grid. To reach 100% electrification rate by 2030 any additional capacity of 1798 MW will be required to supply the demand. About \$ 8 billion will be required for new investments of high share of grid and PV stand-alone solutions corresponding 94.5% (\$ 7.59 billion). In order to supply high demand for stand-alone PV systems it is crucial to consider private investment. It's requires good coordination and planning among differing stakeholders and reform of regulation to accommodate both public and private interests.

References

National Electrification Strategy, 2018

Electrification Plan for Off-Grid Areas, Resolution n.º 52/2023

Energy Transition Strategy, Resolution n.º 61/2023

Master Plan Update Report, volume III, 2012 - 2027

